

The Rivalry of Superpowers in the Horn of Africa during the Ogaden War (1977-1978)

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This article scrutinizes the rivalry of superpowers in the Horn of Africa during the Ogaden War. It mainly examines the Soviet involvement over the Ethiopia-Somalia boundary conflicts (1977-1978). The study utilizes both primary and secondary sources. The archival sources of the study are collected from institutions such as MOFA, ENALA, and IES where aides-memoir, speeches, and exchange of correspondences are consulted. The secondary sources are also collected from various published works. After the data is gathered through various sources, it interpreted through historical methodologies. The finding of the study highlights the conventional wisdom of superpowers' intervention in the Horn of Africa during the Cold War period; it pursues to underscore the complex interplay of the realpolitik of the Soviet foreign policy towards the Horn. It also outlines the Soviet policy perspectives in Africa and its response to the Ogaden War. The result of the study claims that the influence of the Soviet Union in the Horn of Africa generally attracts other powers in the region. Indeed, the Soviet influence in the Horn of Africa escalates the local war into an international dimension. This is therefore; the study concludes the rivalry of superpowers in the Ogaden War was to counterweight their balance of power in the Horn of Africa.

Keywords: ETHIOPIA, THE HORN OF AFRICA, COLD WAR, OGADEN WAR, SUPERPOWER'S COMPETITION.

Introduction

After the third Arab-Israel War, the political atmosphere of some Arab States went through a period of intense radicalization. The strategic position of South Yemen as the entrance to the Red Sea worried the US military planners, mainly after the Angola crisis. When Jimmy Carter had taken over the presidency, he had a grave concern about the Soviet intervention in the Horn and the Middle East (Lefebvre, 1991). This concern had been giving much attention by Brzezinski, the National Security Adviser during the Carter administration. He watched the intensified pattern of Soviet activities in the Horn of Africa. The Soviets appeared as a new ally to Ethiopia during the critical movements of the Ogaden War (1977-1978). The concerns of the Carter administration about the Soviet's decision were escalating the tension in the Horn (Lefebvre, 1991: 55-67).

The 1974 revolution in Ethiopia was the game-changer for Marxist-Leninist inspired transformation in Africa. This revolution took place in the country which defeated colonialism; many people in Africa saw this revolution as embodying Africa's nationalism. In terms of Marxist-Leninist ideology, the Soviets sustained socialism with a strong foundation to withstand the internal problems of the continent (Weiss, 1980:5-9).

To counterweight the US, the Soviets created an alliance with Ethiopia and became an important actor in Africa by establish military bases thousands of miles away from its shores. In a strategic sense, the alliance was also meant to enhance the Soviet influence over the Red Sea and the Indian Ocean. During the Ogaden War, the Soviets delivered an estimated worth of \$1 billion military supply to Ethiopia (Westad, 2003).

However, the Soviet involvement in Ethiopia was not only limited to military support but also to expand socialism in the country. One of the Soviet activities in Ethiopia was to shape the military regime by offering the social and economic reforms (Westad, 2003:274). During the implementation of this reform, there were civil wars, mass starvation, and ethnic-based rebellions in various parts of the country, which led to the gigantic scale of the Soviet involvement in the country.

The basis of the Soviet alliance with Ethiopia had three fundamental reasons. First, the rhetoric of the Ethiopian revolution was matched highly with the Soviet ideology. Second, the Soviets had built trust in Derg's leadership. Third, the victory of the Soviet-Cuban alliance in Angola encouraged the Soviet leaders to intervene more in Africa. The ideological underpinnings of the Derg regime with the Kremlin create a viable long-term alliance for the relationship between the two countries. For the Soviets, the Ethiopian revolution proved a good impetus for the expansion of socialism in Africa. This experience would be crucial for the expansion of socialism in the continent.

Therefore, this study is used an archival sources to solicit viable information on the competition of superpowers in the Horn of Africa, particularly; it aims to analyze the rivalry of superpowers over the Ogaden War (1977-1978).

Materials and methods

This is qualitative research work that utilizes both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources of the study are collected from the institutions of MOFA, ENALA, and IES where aides-memoir, speeches, and exchange of correspondences are consulted. The secondary sources of the study are also collected from various published works (books, articles and internet sources).

The Ogaden War (1977-1978)

Ogaden is situated in the eastern parts of Ethiopia, which is a desert and bleak landscape that slopes from the Harar plateau extend southwards to the Somalia border about 500 meters below sea level. Its size is about 200,000 square kilometres (or 125,000 square miles) (Tareke, 2000). Since independence, the Republic of

Somalia claimed to establish a ‘greater Somali nation’, which is an irredentist movement to incorporate all Somali-speaking peoples in the Horn of Africa.

“If we draw the map of Africa based on religion, race, and language I fear that many states will cease to exist”—Aklilu Habte Wold (Tareke, 2000: 637).

The claim was based on religion, language, and ethnic affiliation. Eventually, the irredentist movement ignited the local war into an international dimension by attracting the involvement of many international actors. After the 1974 creeping coup, Ethiopia seemed a weak state apparatus by Somalia, and Somalia had used this opportunity to incorporate the Ogaden province. This requires Ethiopia to find an alternative ally. Following the decline of the US presence in Ethiopia, the Soviet Union and Cuba's influence were highly intensified.

To counterweight the Soviet involvement in Ethiopia, the US and China support Somalia (Yordanov, 2012). After the abrogation of the Soviet-Somalia friendship treaty, Somalia joined the Arab League club. This membership of Somalia in the Arab league complicated the Soviet-Somalia relations in the Horn of Africa (Lyons, 1978).

As a result, the situation in the Horn of Africa became complicated as many local and international actors were involved to take their sides on the Soviet-Somalia relations. During 1977, the Soviet policy in the Horn had mainly ideological and geostrategic interests. The head of the Soviet international department, Boris Ponomarev, viewed Ethiopia as an ally for ideology while Somalia would remain an ally for expediency since Ponomarev's began to distrust Siad Barre (Wishnick, 1977). It was on an almost daily basis that Ponomarev fed positive reports coming from Ethiopia. As of March 1977; all of the important reports were routinely circulated by the Politburo of Moscow that would achieve its policy goals in the Horn of Africa through Ethiopia.

After the decline of the US presence in Ethiopia, the Soviet representatives in Addis Ababa had changed their patterns of relations towards the Derg regime. For these relations, ambassador Ratanov's political reports to Kremlin were very clear. During the memorandum of understanding held in August 1977, Ratanov presented his overall views for the Military Council and emphasized key questions about who support and oppose Mengistu (Doctoroff, 1977). The hidden agenda for the Military Council was extended to assert because they do not come out openly. According to the leaked information from the Soviet embassy in Addis Ababa, the ‘‘right-wing’’ officials such as Ayalew Mandefro from the Minister of Defense was shipped off to Washington in the later years (Wishnick, 1977). The deputy Chairman of the Derg, Atnafu Abate was also suspected of a nationalist stance that had a high level political and ideological influence in Ethiopian politics. In November 1977, Atnafu was executed along with other officers. The anti-Mengistu forces were receiving support from the US (Tom, 2015). However; the tactics of Mengistu dealing with the real or perceived opponents received the full approval from Ratanov. The Ethiopian leaders who knows the right-wing

representatives were abstained from an open attack and provide them an opportunity to “illustrate the real political challenges” and then “strikes a blow.” Despite his admiration for the characters of Mengistu, the Soviet ambassador admitted such tactics might be dangerous since “the opponents” could organize their support.

During the fall of 1977, Moscow had drawn closer political ties with Ethiopia. By the initiatives of Fidel Castro along with Ali Rubeya, the PDRY leader organized a meeting held in Aden. During this meeting, both Mengistu H. Mariam and Siad Barre were at the negotiation table. However, the meeting was failed and Castro became determined to support Ethiopia.

“Castro was reported to Erich Honecker, leader of East Germany. ‘I have made up my mind about Siad Barre; he is above all a chauvinist. Chauvinism is the most important factor in him. Socialism is just an outer shell that is supposed to make him more attractive.’” Mengistu, on the other hand, strikes me as a quiet, serious, and sincere leader who is aware of the power of the masses. He is an intellectual personality who showed his wisdom on 3 February . . . a very consequential decision was taken on 3 February in Ethiopia” (Westad, 2003).

The position of Barre poses a serious threat to the Ethiopian revolution. The political landscape of Ethiopia was then changed and enabled to take important steps of isolating Somalia. The foreign policy of Barre was focused on Saudi Arabia and other imperial powers (Mengistu, 2011).

After the Aden meeting, Fidel Castro announced that Cuba had decided to send military advisers to Ethiopia and he aptly said that the entire reactionary imperialist powers in Africa would be defeated (Mengistu, 2011). He says that we can free all Africans from the American influence. Castro continued to say that there are crucial developments in Zaire, Libya, and Algeria and the Ethiopia revolution had great revolutionary potentials for other countries. In early 1977, Castro told Honecker, “they should pursue the Soviet policies, principles, and examples.” When the situation in the Horn was complicated, the Soviet leaders thought that their country ought to be refraining from the Ethiopia-Somalia boundary conflicts.

In absence of Brezhnev, Kirilenko has chaired the meeting and stressed that “the situation in the Horn is extremely complicated, “we have no reasons to take sides with either Somalia or Ethiopia, but we have only limited capabilities to influence their mutual relations.” Particularly, after Samantar, the vice president of Somalia visited Moscow in early June 1963, he promised to solve the boundary conflict with Ethiopia peacefully. Kirilenko, Brezhnev, and KGB chief Andropov as well as other skeptics hoped that they would not have to choose between Ethiopia and Somalia (Melvyn and Westad, 2010). Following a personal appeal from Brezhnev, Mengistu had made a promise to make a dialogue with Somalia. Moscow had also doubts whether Ethiopia could meaningfully use an increased amount of the Soviet military equipment or not. The chief of the Cuban military adviser, Arnaldo Ochoa reported that the Mengistu regime had “not yet prepared well for this War.” Conferring to the existing agreements, there was a formal relationship between the two countries. Arnaldo Ochoa was told to Mengistu “a light-headed approach to a serious business might” undermine the prestige of the Military Council.

For Mengistu, however, the situation was getting worse. In the late summer, his response was to assassinate all opponents and imagined enemies by unleashing the “Red Terror” campaign (Jackson, 2007). In September 1977, Jigjiga was annexed by Somalia and Mengistu made a national call for Ethiopians to defend the sovereignty of the country (Fantahun, 2009).

By October, the international department in Moscow concluded that the Mengistu regime would not survive unless a massive military supply from the socialist countries. The Soviet policymakers were also furious about Barre that he had not kept his words to Brezhnev; instead, his offenses continued with the Soviet weapons he had received earlier. When one of the eastern towns in the country bombed by tanks and artillery produced weapons, the Mengistu regime was mourned publicly in Addis Ababa. Advised by the Cuban military advisors and an immediate spectacle shows that the Soviet supports would be needed to save the Mengistu regime. Thus, in October 1977, the Soviet Ambassador (Ratanov) announced that the Soviets halted military supplies to Somalia. Soon the Soviets began to supply massive military assistance to the Mengistu regime to defend the revolution.

For his final straw, Siad Barre had already contacted the Americans (Jackson, 2007). In early November 1977, Barre officially declared that his government had decided to break Somalia’s ties with Moscow by expelling all the Soviet military personnel and closing down the Soviet naval base at the port of Barbara.

Breaking ties with Mogadishu was important for Moscow to engage in a large-scale operation to save the Ethiopian revolution. For about eight months, the Soviets supplied more than \$1 billion worth of military equipment to Ethiopia (Westad, 2003). In late September 1977, two armored battalions were arrived to take part in the Ogaden War from South Yemen (Lee, 2011). Fidel Castro had also contributed around 11,600 Cuban soldiers and more than 6,000 military advisers and technical experts to halt the advance of the Somalia forces (Woodroffe, 2014). On the Soviet side, roughly one thousand Soviet military personals were gone to Ethiopia and organized counter-offensive support.

By early 1978, the tide of the war was in favor of Ethiopia. The deputy commander of the Soviet ground forces, Vasili I. Petrov was in charge of the Ethiopian military planning and organization. Altogether, it was the most important Soviet-led military operation outside the Warsaw Pact since the Korean War. Both Moscow and Havana had necessarily rushed affairs operations in the Horn of Africa. From the outset, the chief military leaders of the Soviets and Cuba insisted that in this operation they would be in control. Unlike the Angola crisis, where many of the allied soldiers felt that the “intrusions” of the Soviet diplomats didn’t mention the Angola leaders had come during the early phases of the Ogaden operation. During the Moscow visit, Mengistu had promised to the Soviet leaders to use their military strategy that would help to maintain the balance of power in the region. Even though some of the crew members were technically operating in Ethiopia, the Soviet-Cuban military support went under the commands of local officers. A quick victory was essential to minimize the losses of the auxiliary troops.

The Soviet-Cuba support for Ethiopia was not only rescuing the revolution, but it had also political and social ramifications. The Mengistu regime received advice that would mobilize the masses to defend the revolution (Laitin, 1976). The Soviets had sent experts to Addis Ababa to support the Ethiopian revolution.

The Mengistu regime had receive a warning from Brezhnev about the question of nationalities in Ethiopia. Brezhnev said Moscow would not intervene again to support Mengistu to defeat the insurgents in Ethiopia. The message was very clear to Mengistu after defeating the invading forces of Somalia. After the victory of Ethiopia over Somalia, it was very difficult to convince the Mengistu regime to create a party from all bases of the Ethiopian society. Establishing the inclusive party became an illusion and Ratanov had complained about it during his visit to East German.

It was, therefore, important to establish a party to take the lead along with other capable forces (inside and outside) of Ethiopia. If the forces around Mengistu do not succeed in this fight, the central committee would not establish the party. The Mengistu regime has been lately devoted to establishing a single party. In between, great confusion existed concerning the ideological questions as well as strategies.

The Soviet advisers were to reduce atrocities among the left-wing as well as the brutal treatment of the Derg regime. The head of the international department, Comrade Ponomarev had deeply expressed his concern about the extremist stance of the revolution. After he talked to Mengistu, comrade Rau' l Valde's Vivo' had already stated that the summary executions of the opponents would not be advantageous to the revolution. After the Somalia forces are being driven out from Ogaden, Ponomarev told his East German counterparts, the internal contradictions in Ethiopia were not yet ameliorated. Ratanov had also exclaimed "Mengistu had no a concept of cooperation with the Soviet advisers regarding installing the internal reforms" (Westad, 2003).

In March 1978, the Ethiopian army along with the Cuba auxiliary forces recaptured Jijiga (Ayle, 2009). However, after the end of the Ogaden war, guerrilla fighting persisted until the Lash operation (the whole 1980s). Without outside support, Somalia's regular army had no chance to fight the allied forces of the enemy. Politically as well as diplomatically, the Barre regime had also overstated his case. Despite the consequences of the Ethiopian revolution, the core Somali ethnicity in Ogaden expected a general rise of other nationalities that did not yet occur inside Ethiopia. In diplomatic terms, due to Barr's action, Somalia was isolated from Muslim and non-Muslim countries in Africa.

The Soviet involvement in the Horn was viewed as a positive and advantageous accomplishment. The intervention and operation of the Soviets in the Horn were viewed as an important stepping stone for the expansion of Socialism, and to halt the progressive and radical Arab states that would expand their position in the region.

The CPSU leadership in Moscow was highly impressed by the successful operation of Ethiopia against Somalia. In post-World War II, the Soviet involvement in the Horn was a real gesture for the global power contenders that could show its determination in the third world. Angola had already set the pattern of such Soviet involvement in Africa and carried out the coordination and planning of the Soviet Union and Cuba (Lee, 2011). The General Staff of the Soviet-Cuba allied forces had got lucky pictures in Angola. Ethiopia was different because it was not only the Soviet military planners that commanded the operation, but also the Cuban fighting troops were almost there as the auxiliary troops. The Soviets were the ultimate decider of the relationship between Ethiopia and Somalia in a far-away conflict. In other words, the boundary conflicts of the two countries had become a fertile ground for the rivalry of superpowers in the Horn of Africa.

In 1976/77, the Soviet advisers came to Ethiopia with all excitement in the making of the Ethiopian revolution. They believed that this revolution could influence the political fates of the African countries (Westad, 2003). For the Soviet advisers, Ethiopia was the only country in Africa that resisted colonialism; and the country that attracts a significant number of Russian travellers and explorers during the 19th century. Ethiopia is also the country that confessed with a similar form of Orthodox religion. Besides, it was believed that Ethiopia had a similar pattern to the Soviet revolution. However; the Soviet leaders defined the Ethiopian revolution in narrow terms that seems a grand challenge for the transformational of socialism.

Why the Horn became the bone of contention for superpowers during the Ogaden War?

Since the fall of 1977, the Soviet involvement in Ethiopia was intensified. By early 1979, there were about seven thousand Soviet and Cuban military experts in Ethiopia (Zhihua, 2000). The Soviet advisers and experts were in place to oversee the influence of socialism in Ethiopia. The bureaucrats in Ethiopia were being trained in the Soviet Union or other East European socialist countries. The international department in Moscow was working overtime to supply the number of experts that needed for a smooth process of the Ethiopian revolution.

The Soviet political advisers in Ethiopia could take charges for a smooth run of the revolution while the soldiers could set the country towards socialism. Mengistu heartily agreed that the shortcoming of the revolution had not been equipped with the ideology of the working-class. Thus, Mengistu declared that the setting up of the commission for the Organization of the Workers' Party of Ethiopia [WPE] (Tiruneh, 1993). However, during the establishment of the Workers Party, the Soviet advisers understood that the Derg had already made purges significant number of Ethiopians, or driven out the elites into exile. The Soviets wanted Mengistu to make peace with some of the surviving left-wing leaders and consolidate the WPE. Understandably, Mengistu was refused to accept this deal.

By 1979, the Soviet advisers in Addis Ababa advised Mengistu to establish the Marxist-Leninist party. The efforts to establish the Marxist party could be in existence. Before the establishment of the Workers' Party,

the Soviet influence was in decline. The other big challenge for the Soviets in Ethiopia was the on-going war with the various insurgents in the country.

The internal conflicts became troublesome to the Ethiopian allies because the insurgents such as the Eritrean People's Liberation Front (EPLF) had also pursued the Marxist-Leninist ideology. Until 1975, the EPLF had received Soviet military and technical supports. However, finding a peaceful solution between the Mengistu leadership with EPLF was not an easy task. The position of the Soviets in Eritrea was to give autonomy, but both sides rejected the proposal. The EPLF claimed that the former friends were pressing to give up the fundamental goals of independence.

Privately, Mengistu told his Moscow friends any deal with the EPLF "would throw him to the nationalist wolves." Karen Brutents attempts to enlist Cuba, East German, and Palestinian assistance in working out some forms of compromise, but Mengistu made a formal request to his allies not to send supplies to the EPLF.

By February 1978, the vice president of Cuba, Carlos Rafael Rodriguez reported to Fidel Castro, "we cannot afford to make any mistakes in handling the Eritrea problem" (Westad, 2003: 259). He continually said that a wrong move could endanger our entire policy in Africa, and we would be confronted by the majority of the African states, thus, we oppose any military intervention in Eritrea.

The two sides met at East Berlin and found a solution. The attempt of Honecker to get Soviet support dictates the compromise of the Mengistu regime with the EPLF leaders. In early April, East Germany had learned that the Soviet advisers began to participate in the War and advanced the Soviet weapons for the insurgents in Eritrea. All steps and initiatives on the CPSU, the CP Cuba, and the SED must be put forward extremely either tactfully not to cause any protest, Ulianovskii explained to the East German in May and admitted, "the problem lies a certain degree in the fact that we all attempt to square the circle." A few months after the decisive victory, the Soviet's enthusiasm towards the Mengistu regime was begun to deteriorate.

Despite all its support, during the meeting with the Politburo in July 1978, Maltsev complained about the Mengistu regime neither to get Eritrea nor the Ogaden problem. Kirilenko viewed Mengistu as a "sensible person," whose main problem was lack of experience after he chaired Politburo meeting. Kirilenko had also concluded that it is better to educate and expose him. In connection with Ethiopia, Andropov and Ponomarev reminded that "they show Mengistu on his side." While other members from the Politburo worried about how to control the Ethiopian situation, particularly, Ponomarev stressed that "Cuba will not do anything about Ethiopia without the prior knowledge of the Soviets."

For the Soviets, Ethiopian socialism was being reduced to troublesome charges. While the Soviet leaders had been agonizing over the Horn of Africa, the concern of the Carter administration had surged (Jackson, 2007). Likewise; the Carter administration realized there would be no quick breakthrough with the Soviet Union over the nuclear arms limitation deal. President Carter became very sensitive to the right-wing pressure and

conceded to the Soviets.

However, in late 1977, the Carter administration was leaning towards a tougher policy in the Horn of Africa. Brzezinski concluded in his memoirs that the Soviet intervention in the Horn of Africa creates a crisis, and he said the “détente lies buried in the sands of the Ogaden” (Woodroffe, 2014:74). After the victory of Ethiopia over Somalia, President Carter had a grave concern “over the Soviet effort to increase its intervention in Africa.” Carter asked Gromyko to report Brezhnev as an “alarming development in the Horn of Africa” (Schulzinger, 2010).

During the crisis in the Horn, Brzezinski’s view over the Soviet policy had clashed with Cyrus Vance (the secretary of the state department) (Woodroffe, 2014:74). Vance believed that the Soviet intervention in Ethiopia should not be allowed to create trouble for the strategic arms limitation deal while Brzezinski held that “if we don’t react, we destroyed our regional and international position—and we create the condition of the domestic reaction.” Cyrus Vance opposed Brzezinski’s proposal to support Somalia, by moving the US naval task force in the Horn of Africa, and issuing a joint Sino-US condemnation, and cancelling the space and trade talks with the Soviets. Vance told Brzezinski, “this is where you and I apart, and the consequences of doing something like this are dangerous.” In the end, the US reaction was limited and the crisis of the two officials helped Brzezinski to win the good images of the president. As a result, the Carter speech in June 1978 claimed that “détente with the Soviet Union seemingly continue to struggle in a variety of ways. The Soviet military aid and influence in the third world was expanded tremendously. Finally, agreeing to send Brzezinski to Beijing, President Carter requests China to provide aid to Somalia (use China as the playing Card to counterweight the Soviets in the Horn) (Woodroffe, 2014; New York Times, April 1978).

However, the measures of Carter were too little and too late. During Ronald Reagan’s presidential election campaign, he ridiculed the Soviet’s action in the Horn in apocalyptic terms “if the Soviets are not controlled, they would have more and more influence in the entire region (Lefebvre, 1991). He continues to criticize “if the Soviets influence in the Horn continued, Moscow would able to destabilize the anti-communist governments in the Arab states. . . in a few years, we may face with the prospects of the Soviet empire in the protégés and dependencies that stretched from Addis Ababa to Cape Town.

In 1978, the Soviet policymakers were unaware of the Third World that affects the future détente with the US. To Brezhnev and his circles, the principle of equality would have been established in consultation with the Nixon administration; it was not only entitled them to intervene in these areas but also to separate the Third World from the United States. After all, the Americans had not to request Moscow to intervene against the Allende government or any other leftist movement in the third world.

By the mid-1970s, the overall political developments in the Third World were shifted towards the left. The Soviet Union had been able to protect, assist and guide some of the Third World radical movements through

the revolutionary institutions. The US may protest these developments while the Soviets felt at the end, Washington would not risk wrecking the overall process of détente because the poor countries were far away from the strategic location of superpowers.

It would take several years before the Soviet leadership had begun to understand the US political elites and resist the competition with the Soviets. However, before Moscow realized the Third World influence, the opinion of détente with the US started to diverge within the Soviet leadership in the Third World. Spurred by the Ethiopian revolution, a few Soviet experts began to characterize some of the national-democratic revolutions in the Third World. The issue was the degree that the Mengistu regime initiated the transition of socialism through the class-based action from below. In other words, the Soviet and its allies support such a regime that would stand to risk the next stages of the Ethiopian revolution.

Oleg Bogomolov, the head of the Institute of Economy of the World Socialist System (IEMSS), and Evgeni Primakov, the head of the Institute of Oriental Studies (IOS) were among the influential academia centered on the various questions. Some of the “progressive” regimes in the third world were inability to form the united front with the local bourgeoisie and represent the principle of “Bonapartism” from the economic and social changes to develop the working class.

By the end of 1978, the disenchantment of the Soviets in the Third World had spill-over effects on the key government institutions, particularly the international department and the KGB. Within these institutions, it is striking that the involvement of the Soviets in the Third World was highly intensified during Angola and the Horn of Africa crisis. A series of devastating memoranda, Boris Ponomarev, the deputy of MO had sent his boss between January and June 1979, believed that building socialism in the Third World was the Soviet project while the local inputs remained minimal.

Conclusion

After the end of World War II, the Horn of Africa was one of the strategic places that attracted the rivalry of superpowers. By the end of 1970, the influence of the Soviets in Africa was very high and the purpose of its influence was to guide international revolutions.

After the 1974 Ethiopian revolution, the Derg leaderships had maintained the same foreign policy of the imperial regime. Initially, Ethiopia’s non-aligned position allowed the Derg regime to seek military aid from all sources such (Washington, Beijing, or Moscow). Yet, the international actors were hesitant to respond to the military aid requested by the Derg regime. Owing to the internal challenges and external threats, the Derg leaders were intended to ‘shop’ the military supply from all possible sources.

Eventually, Ethiopia was begun to contemplate its foreign policy reorientation. The key reason for this policy reorientation was coming after the decline of the US military aid to Ethiopia. This policy shift was made to gain immediate military aid to Ethiopia’s external threat. Throughout the Ethiopian revolution, the military

power control over the civilian government had been growing the possibility of the Derg leaders to ally with the socialist bloc.

After Ethiopia receive a reduced amount of military supply from the US, the Derg leaders were begun to cast an alternative ally for the urgent military need to the external threats.

Like Angola, the Soviets had a fierce arms race competition with the US in the Horn of Africa. Before the Sino-American détente, the US used the Horn as a means of détente with the Soviets by attempting to use China's card. In between these challenges, the Sino-US rapprochement reassured the US deliberation to ally itself with China against the Soviets. Brzezinski's calculation of creating an alliance with China against the Soviets would increase the US leverage over the Soviet Union in the Horn. The US attempts to use China's card to persuade the Soviets into acceptable behavior in the third world. The Carter administration accepted Brzezinski's idea and sent him to Beijing over Vance on May 20, 1978.

From the outset, due to the ideological underpinnings with the Derg regime, the US had a very limited option in the Ogaden War. The involvement of the Soviets over the Ogaden War was a straightforward policy that justified its presence in the Horn of Africa.

Conclusively, after the US had lost the Vietnam War, the Ogaden War became another battleground for the rivalry of superpowers in the Horn of Africa. As Modelski surmised "every internal war creates a demand for foreign intervention, Ethiopia's location at the strategic location of the Red Sea and the Indian Ocean attracts other contending powers in the region. This competition made the Ogaden War into a more complicated and international war. The Soviet and its allies were fought against Somalia using Ethiopia while the US fought against Ethiopia using Somalia to counterweight their presences in the Horn of Africa.

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